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1 МАХСУС СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ
СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

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SPECIAL ISSUE 1

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

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ASSESSMENT OF CLINICO-ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF PREHOSPITAL CARE THROMBOLYSIS USING STREPTOKINASE

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ABSTRACT

In our country, 20 million patients are registered annually cardiovascular diseases, which are the cause of death of more than 1.2 million people [1]. It should be noted that in 20% of cases it is death at working age. The leading reason in the structure of mortality from cardiovascular diseases is coronary heart disease - 8.1% (431 per 100 thousand population). Death from a heart attack myocardial infarction in our country is 45 per 100 thousand of the population, the average hospital mortality rate in the country's hospitals varies from 19 to 28% [1].

Keywords: ST elevation myocardial infarction, reperfusion, thrombolysis, streptokinase, percutaneous coronary intervention.

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ОЦЕНКА КЛИНИКО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРОВЕДЕНИЯ ДОГОСПИТАЛЬНОГО ТРОМБОЛИЗИСА С ПРИМЕНЕНИЕМ СТРЕПТОКИНАЗЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В нашей регионе ежегодно регистрируется 20 млн больных сердечнососудистыми заболеваниями, являющимися причиной смерти более 1,2 млн человек [1]. Нельзя не отметить тот факт, что в 20% случаев это смерть в трудоспособном возрасте. Ведущей причиной в структуре смертности от сердечнососудистых заболеваний является ишемическая болезнь сердца — 8,1% (431 на 100 тыс. населения). Смертность от инфаркта миокарда в нашей стране составляет 45 на 100 тыс. населения, средняя госпитальная летальность колеблется в стационарах страны от 19 до 28% [1].

Ключевые слова: инфаркт миокарда с подъемом ST, реперфузия, тромболизис, спретокиназа, чрескожное коронарное вмешательство.

**Пулатова Ш.Х.,
Шаропов У.Р.**

СТРЕПТНОКИНАЗА БИЛАН ЎТКАЗИЛГАН ГОСПИТАЛ ЭТАПГАЧА ТРОМБОЛИТИК ТЕРАПИЯНИНГ КЛИНИКО-ИҚТИСОДИЙ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ БАҲОЛАШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Бизнинг мамлакатимизда ҳар йили аҳолининг 20 млн юрак-қон томир касалликларидан, 1,2 млн ўлимнинг сабаби бўлиб қолди. Шунинг таъкидлаш жоизки, шуларнинг 20% меҳнатга лайёқатли ёшда тўғри келмоқда [1]. Ўлимнинг асосий сабаби юрак ишемик касаллигини – 8,1% (431 ҳар 100 минг аҳолига тўғри келади). Шулардан бизнинг мамлакатимизда, ўткир миокард инфарктдан кейинги ўлим 45 ҳар бир 100 минг аҳолига тўғри келади, шулардан госпитал леталлик 19 дан-28% ташкил қилади [1].

Калит сўзлар: ST сегменти кўтарилиши билан кечадиган миокард инфарти, реперфузия, тромболитик терапия, стрептокиназа, тери ости коронар аралашув.

Introduction. Given the scale and social significance of the problem, in 2008 Russia adopted a federal program to implement measures aimed at improving the provision of medical care for patients with vascular disease. To date, as a result of the implementation of program activities, a decrease in mortality from myocardial infarction in 2009 by 4.6% has been achieved. Compared with 2007 [2], however, this problem remains relevant and requires a systematic approach to the solution.

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the clinical and cost-effectiveness of various reperfusion strategies for ST elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI), including prehospital thrombolysis using streptokinase.

Materials and methods: The main research method was selected cost-effectiveness analysis. For the analysis, a model of care for patients with STEMI in the region "C" was built. It is estimated that 4.39 million people live in Region C, of which 83% is urban. Total number of patients with myocardial infarction in the region, information about which is included in the register, 1477 [3], while the proportion of patients included in the register is 66%. Thus, we made an assumption that the total number of MI in the analyzed region was 2238 cases. The proportion of patients with STEMI from the total number of MI in the analyzed region according to the registry - 42%, which corresponds to 940 cases of STEMI.

Simulated reperfusion strategies:

- 1) No reperfusion.
- 2) Primary percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) in the group of patients where PCI can be performed within 120 min [4] from the onset of symptoms, the group of the remaining patients without reperfusion.
- 3) Primary PCI in the group of patients when it is possible to perform PCI within 120 minutes from the moment onset of symptoms, in the group of remaining patients - carrying out thrombolysis in a hospital with the use of streptokinase.
- 4) Primary PCI in the group of patients when it is possible to perform PCI within 120 minutes from the moment onset of symptoms, in the group of remaining patients - carrying out thrombolysis in a hospital with the use of tenecteplase.
- 5) Primary PCI in the group of patients when it is possible to perform PCI within 120 minutes from the moment onset of symptoms, in the group of remaining patients prehospital thrombolysis with tenecteplase.
- 6) Primary PCI in the group of patients when it is possible to perform PCI within 120 minutes from the moment onset of symptoms, in the group of remaining patients - pre-hospital thrombolysis with tenecteplase if no more than 4 hours have passed since the onset of symptoms, in the remaining patients, the decision on the advisability of conducting thrombolysis is taken in a hospital, in case of a positive decision - thrombolysis with streptokinase.

Research results: "Strategy #1". No reperfusion. According to register of acute coronary syndromes (ACS) [3], in Russia this group of patients is currently declining, but in general remains significant. Thus, in 2008 the share patients with STEMI who underwent reperfusion therapy was 32.98%. In 2009 after the beginning of the implementation of the activities of the program to improve the provision of medical care for patients with vascular disease, this indicator amounted to 54.14%. In European countries, in particular in France, the proportion of patients with STEMI who underwent reperfusion (PCI + thrombolysis) in 2000 was 66%, and by 2006 it was already 95% [4].

In the absence of reperfusion, according to international studies and registries, 30-day mortality is 18.4% [10], within 1 year - 21.5% [2], 5 years 29%, and 25 years 82% [5]. in the group of the remaining patients - thrombolysis in a hospital with the use of alteplase. Since the leading value in the treatment of STEMI has a time of care (reperfusion) from the onset of symptoms, when choosing of this strategy, the key point is the location, namely the distance from PCI centers and specialized hospitals.

To model predicted mortality in within 30 days, data from the Vienna Registry were used, according to which the mortality rate during thrombolysis earlier than 120 minutes — 4.2%; 121-180 min 4.6%; 180-360 min 4.5%; more than 360 min — 7.7% [6]. The data received also correspond to USIC Registry data (includes 1922 patients), according to which the 30-day mortality rate for in-hospital thrombolysis is 7%, lethality within a year is 11% [19]. Mortality within 5 and 25 years was 19% and 76%, respectively [3].

"Strategy No. 4". Primary PCI in the group of patients where PCI can be performed within 120 minutes from the onset of symptoms, in the group of the remaining patients - thrombolysis in a hospital using streptokinase.

This strategy differs from the previous one in the choice of a drug for thrombolysis, it was singled out by us separately in order to assess the impact drug selection on cost and cost effectiveness.

"Strategy No. 5". Primary PCI in the group of patients where PCI can be performed within 120 minutes from the onset of symptoms, in the group of the remaining patients, pre-hospital thrombolysis with streptokinase was performed.

The main advantage of prehospital thrombolysis is the ability to reduce the systemic delay during reperfusion by an average of 60 min [20], which was confirmed by meta-analysis data [2]. For rural residents' terrain, the system delay time can be reduced by 120 minutes or more.

During prehospital thrombolysis the incidence of cardiogenic shock is significantly less than with inpatient PCI: 1.3% and 5.3% ($p=0.032$), respectively [2]. a fact in favor of prehospital thrombolysis is the frequency of abortive infarction myocardium during reperfusion. Yes, at prehospital thrombolysis abortive course STEMI is observed in 20% of cases, while in hospital thrombolysis, the number of abortive infarcts did not exceed 13.3% [3]. share reduction. Complicated STEMI can achieve improvement in hospital mortality rates. According to international studies and registries, prehospital thrombolysis can reduce 30-day mortality to 3.3% [19] - 4.4% [5], mortality during the first year is 5.3%] – 6.0% [4]. There are no separate data on the effect of prehospital thrombolysis on long-term outcomes. In this relationship to assess mortality after 5 and 25 years, data from cohort patients with reperfusion were used, regardless of the type and timing: 5 years 19% and 25 years old 76% [2].

Considering the distribution of the flow of patients in time (according to the ASSENT 3 study), with this strategy chosen, about 60% of patients can receive thrombolysis at the prehospital stage. Mortality in the hospital (30 days), as well as during first year was assessed for each subgroup (primary PCI + prehospital thrombolysis + inpatient thrombolysis) using a methodology similar to consistent with previous strategies. Pooled data on the impact of the choice of reperfusion strategy in the analyzed region "C" are given.

3) The cost of PCI was estimated based on the tariff for the provision of high-tech medical care for 2022 [5] with the assumption that that the costs of this intervention do not depend on whether This assistance is provided routinely or urgently.

4) The cost of thrombolysis with tenecteplase included the cost of the drug, because the administration system is supplied with the drug. According to the Pharmexpert analytical base, the

average wholesale cost of a package of streptokinase 1.5 million for 2022 amounted to 180,000 soums.

Discussion. The problem of mortality from cardiovascular diseases remains extremely relevant in Russia and requires a systematic approach to the solution. Choice is possible different patient care strategies with STEMI in each specific region, taking into account local features, but, nevertheless, some patterns may be common for different subjects.

The introduction of primary PCI leads to decrease in mortality compared with the absence of reperfusion, but does not solve the problem cardinally for a number of reasons, one of which is time transportation to the PCI center, which is especially important for residents of rural areas and small towns. The system delay time for these regions makes primary PCI is an inaccessible type of care for residents of these areas. Moreover, in terms of cost for saved life and saved years of life is the most expensive type of reperfusion.

Performing primary PCI in the proportion of patients which fit into the "therapeutic window" in accordance with the recommendations, and in the remaining patients, thrombolysis in a hospital allows to achieve a greater reduction in mortality. In this case, the choice of drug for reperfusion affects the level of additional costs.

The most effective strategy for performing primary PCI is within the "therapeutic window", in the remaining patients with STEMI, thrombolysis at the prehospital stage. Decreased mortality due to a reduction in systemic delay during reperfusion, which is especially important for residents of remote regions, since allows them to get the help they need in more early dates. It should be noted that, from a cost-effectiveness point of view, thrombolysis at the prehospital stage, using tenecteplase is more economically feasible than using it for thrombolysis in a hospital setting.

Conclusion. Model of care for patients with a heart attack myocardium with ST segment elevation with conduction primary PCI within the first 120 minutes of symptom onset and if PCI within the specified time frame is impossible, pre-hospital thrombolysis with the use of drugs bolus administration is economically the most effective and allows to achieve the greatest reduction in mortality in patients with STEMI.

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